

Cutting Mechanics-Informed Explainable AI for Surface Roughness Prediction

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Abstract

The rising demand for high-quality machined parts for precision manufacturing and the complexity of machining processes highlight the need for real-time monitoring to maintain product quality. This study proposes a novel methodology for predicting surface roughness in Computer numerical control (CNC) machining in up-milling and down-milling operations. By leveraging cutting force signals within an Explainable AI (XAI) framework, the approach offers insights into the machining process with the help of physics-based cutting mechanics. Focusing on machining with carbide inserts featuring a wiper geometry, this work combines force signal monitoring using a piezoelectric sensor and online surface roughness measurements using a chromatic confocal sensor. A lobe-based localized feature extraction methodology is introduced, inspired by the chip formation mechanisms in up and down-milling. To balance predictive accuracy and computational efficiency for real-time manufacturing with limited data, a two-step machine learning model was implemented instead of a deep learning based approach. Thus, a classifier model was developed to distinguish between up and down milling, followed by regression models to predict surface roughness. Random Forest (RF) and Support Vector Machines (SVM) were selected for their balance between accuracy and interpretability, making them ideal for the industry-relevant data set. The results demonstrated improved surface finish prediction accuracy, aligning with zero-defect manufacturing (ZDM) principles.

The rising demand for high-quality machined parts in precision manufacturing and the complexity of machining processes highlight the need for real-time monitoring to ensure product quality. This study presents a physics-informed methodology for predicting surface roughness parameters in CNC milling, combining tailored feature extraction, machine learning, and interpretability. Force signals were acquired with a piezoelectric dynamometer, while surface roughness was measured online using a chromatic confocal sensor. A lobe-based feature extraction strategy, inspired by chip formation mechanics, was developed to capture localized process information. This was applied to both up- and down-milling with wiper inserts, which are widely used in industry but rarely investigated in surface quality prediction. The engineered dataset was evaluated using a two-step machine learning framework: first classifying milling mode (up vs. down), then predicting roughness parameters. Random Forests and Support Vector Machines were selected for their balance between accuracy and interpretability. Results show that the extracted features encode sufficient physics to support both classification and regression tasks. Predictions were obtained for multiple parameters, including R_a , R_p , R_{sk} , and R_{ku} , with comparative analysis presented. Beyond accuracy, the approach emphasizes physics-informed and interpretable modeling, where statistical findings are consistently linked to machining mechanics, and Explainable AI (XAI) ensures model transparency and suitability for online deployment. This methodology bridges machining science and AI, aligning with the objectives of zero-defect manufacturing (ZDM).

Keywords: milling process, smart manufacturing, surface roughness, cutting forces, explainable AI.

1. Introduction

The highly competitive industrial landscape fuels the demand for high-quality manufacturing parts. Even with modern technology that improves machining quality, a lack of process monitoring can lead to faults, making quality control difficult to achieve [1]. Intelligent automation in Computer Numerical Control (CNC) machines and sophisticated machine tool controls are critical for assuring product quality, dimensional accuracy, and compliance with customer and industry requirements [2]. Although high-end equipment can enhance machining quality to some extent, the lack of monitoring processes can still result in numerous defects, making engineering quality control a significant challenge [3], [4]. However, with the advent of Industry 4.0, the digitalization of machining operations has enabled access to massive volumes of data, creating opportunities to improve machining quality by leveraging machine-learning techniques [5].

While Industry 4.0 focuses on the digitalization and interconnectivity of manufacturing processes, Industry 5.0 emphasizes sustainability and human-centric manufacturing [6]. The shift from Industry 4.0 to Industry 5.0 reflects a broader goal of achieving Zero-Defect Manufacturing (ZDM)

while minimizing environmental impact, and fostering collaboration between machines and human intelligence [7]. By leveraging machine learning and explainable AI (XAI), manufacturers can identify potential issues in the machining processes and make informed adjustments to avoid defects, enhancing product quality and reducing the scrapping of non-conforming parts. One such important quality of a manufactured part is surface roughness. Moreover, it is crucial for product performance and service life, which is typically measured offline, causing delays in physical defect detection, downtime, and limited adaptability with variable interpretability. Predicting surface quality through monitored signals can provide a more efficient solution to optimize workpiece quality in real time [8]. To solve this issue, this article focuses on combining force signal monitoring with Explainable AI (XAI) to predict surface roughness, providing deeper insights into machining operations and building trust in the AI model, which is commonly seen as a black box [9]. During data collection, surface roughness was assessed with a non-contact chromatic confocal sensor, allowing on-machine measurements without the risk of scratches induced by typical stylus-based approaches [10].

Furthermore, it is important to acknowledge that the direct relationship between cutting force and surface roughness is a challenging issue in machining [11]. Although a relationship between these variables exists, a definitive correlation has not been established due to the complexity of the interaction. This relationship is highly dependent on numerous factors, including tool material and geometry, workpiece material properties, cutting mode, machine dynamics, cutting fluid application, etc. Furthermore, the complex nature of material removal operations adds to the complexity, since chip formation, tool wear, and heat generation may all significantly influence cutting force and surface roughness [12].

However, we already know that the physical relationship between chip formation, tool wear, heat generation, and cutting force is understood but mathematically too complex to be fully described showing high non-linearity. We therefore propose an AI-based approach that takes advantage of understanding the physics of the cutting process during feature extraction with the help of the lobe-based approach. This allows for better data utilization by focusing on relevant cutting process dynamics while improving the model performance without necessitating the need for deriving an equation that unifies all the process variables.

With the help of a 3-axis piezoelectric force sensor, the cutting forces were recorded during up and down cutting modes for milling. A methodology is then proposed for processing the force signals. The surface roughness of the machined surfaces was measured using an on-machine setup with a chromatic confocal sensor. Unlike the majority of works found in the smart manufacturing literature, the database generated in this work is more aligned with real industry practices, as it employs carbide inserts with the wiper feature. This feature represents a modification of the tool nose geometry designed to improve surface finish by producing surfaces with considerably lower roughness. Unlike standard inserts that focus on material removal, wiper

inserts create a finer surface by leaving fewer tool marks [13]. However, with the presence of these inserts, the correlation between the machining parameters becomes more complex as it can maintain a good finish even at higher feed rates unlike traditional ones [14]. From the state-of-the-art literature studied, no article has been found dealing with an AI-aided approach to correlate machining parameters for machining with wiper inserts. Apart from this, tool radial engagement during milling was not constant during every single cutting pass, which made the experimental data closer to the industry standard.

Further, the extracted features from the force signals along with the process parameters were used to predict the surface roughness. But often having results is not enough as it is sometimes difficult to explain the behavior of the model which leads us to the results and is often treated as a black box approach [15]. Thus, using the feature importance attribute we explain the prediction results of the models using an Explainable AI (XAI) approach which aims to make complex AI models transparent and interpretable, enabling users to understand decisions, identify biases, and ensure accountability [9].

The main contributions of this work are:

1. A tailored lobe-based feature extraction strategy inspired by chip formation mechanics, enabling more informative features than direct force signal extraction. This includes analysis of both up- and down-milling with wiper inserts, which are widely used in industry but rarely studied in the context of Ra prediction. To the best of the authors' knowledge, no similar work has addressed this.
2. A two-step machine learning framework, where the engineered features first allow classification of milling mode (up vs. down) before predicting surface roughness, demonstrating that the dataset encodes sufficient process physics for both tasks.
3. Physics-informed and interpretable modeling, where statistical results are consistently linked to machining mechanics, and Explainable AI (XAI) is used to enhance interpretability and facilitate on-machine applicability..

The article presents an approach that utilizes cutting forces to predict surface roughness. From the authors' perspective, this method can be applied in industrial settings. Several sensor options are available for implementation, including dynamometers, strain gauges, and even a simpler solution that integrates a load cell pin into the machine structure.

Following the introduction, the **State of the Art** reviews related research and highlights the gap addressed in this work. The **Theoretical Background** outlines surface roughness concepts, machine learning models, and Explainable AI. The **Materials, Methods and Experimental Design** section describes the machining setup and materials used, while **Data Processing and**

Downstream Analysis details the experimental workflow and model evaluation. The **Results and Discussion** present the findings, and the paper concludes with **Conclusion and Future Research**.

2. State of the Art

Monitoring of machining signals like cutting force, power, energy, etc. are critical components of intelligent machining processes [16]. It gives useful information on the limits of cutting conditions, workpiece surface quality, and tool wear. For example, cutting force monitoring may identify and avoid tool breakage and chatter, compensate for tool deflections, and improve machining operations using model-based adaptive control systems and other process information [17]. These characteristics are critical for successful process feedback control [18], [19].

Research into evaluating the surface roughness of a workpiece using an AI-aided approach is an increasingly popular subject in academia and industry. To correlate surface roughness with machining parameters [20], [21], data from sensors such as vibration [22], [23], [24], [25], [26], acoustic emission [27], [28], [29], power [30], [31], temperature [32], [33] can be used to record the dynamic behavior of the machining process. These sensor signals give information about cutting tool interactions, material removal methods, and tool wear [34], all of which affect surface finishing. Advanced AI models can be constructed by combining sensor data and roughness measures to predict surface quality based on real-time monitoring [35]. This approach improves knowledge of the complicated interactions between process variables and machined surface properties, resulting in better process control and product quality.

Many researchers employ deep learning models based on images to predict surface roughness. The research carried out by Sun et al. [36] attempted to preprocess surface texture orientation and position correction in optical images produced by photographing surface roughness samples with a camera. They were then trained using Residual Network (ResNet), a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)-based deep learning architecture that detects and predicts surface roughness. The work presents an interesting approach to surface roughness evaluation using machine vision and AI, but a potential limitation lies in the reliance on 2D imaging, which may not fully capture the 3D surface characteristics critical for high-precision quality control (QC) in monitoring cutting processes. Apart from that, de Agustina et al. [37] researched robot-assisted polishing, extracting force signals from workpieces and comparing them to surface roughness measures. The study effectively leverages force signal features for surface roughness estimation, however, its reliance on offline roughness measurements limits real-time applicability, which is crucial for cutting process optimization. Yeganefar et al. [38] presented a Support Vector Machine (SVM) model for predicting the appropriate surface roughness and cutting power while milling aluminum alloys. It provides a thorough comparison of predictive models, but the lack of integration with real-time monitoring systems reduces its practical relevance for quality control in industrial milling processes. Deshpande et al. [39] investigated the relationship between machining force, sound,

and vibration signals from turning Inconel 718 with the resulting machined surface roughness. Using a combination of cutting parameters and process responses, their proposed regression model scored an accuracy metric of 90%. Another work from Wu et al. [40] introduced a novel deep learning-based model to predict surface roughness during milling of γ -TiAl alloy. Utilizing continuous wavelet transform for feature extraction and transfer learning for improved speed and accuracy, the proposed method achieved up to 98% classification accuracy. However, its reliance on classification instead of regression limits the precision of surface quality predictions necessary for QC in industrial cutting processes. In another work of Ming et al. [41], the authors predicted the roughness parameters in ultrasonic vibration-assisted milling based on the reconstructed surface topography matrices generated using tool runout, vibration, and deflection. The study excels in integrating geometric, kinematic, and dynamic factors into a comprehensive model for predicting surface roughness in ultrasonic vibration-assisted milling (UVAM), demonstrating a robust understanding of process dynamics. The research done by the Papandrea et al. [42] proposes a non-intrusive quality monitoring method using the correlation between acoustic emission and surface roughness with AISI 52100 hardened steel using Principal Component Analysis [43]. However, the methodology's dependence on PCA for feature reduction may limit its scalability in more complex, noisy environments where diverse cutting conditions and tool wear could affect the sound pattern.

Conventional machine learning approaches, regardless of their potential, encounter constraints in intricate settings, thus necessitating the investigation of computer vision methodologies to enhance quality control in manufacturing.

In works utilizing computer vision, Huang et al. [44] applied a 1D-CNN model with XYZ accelerometers and microphones to evaluate surface roughness and tool wear using vibration and sound inputs. Rifai et al. [45] used computer vision techniques to examine ridge-valley patterns on machining surfaces and extracted features with CNNs. Similarly, in [46], a 2D-CNN was used to identify surface roughness during end-milling operations. The authors stressed the choice of the optimizer for the model to get the best possible class-wise accuracy of 96.3%. However, these studies could be strengthened by further validating the model under diverse machining conditions and considering its robustness in real-time, noisy industrial environments.

Building on the advancements in traditional machine learning and deep learning approaches for quality control in machining, the need for enhanced interpretability has led to the development of Explainable AI (XAI). As AI models become more complex, XAI has become essential to ensure transparency, accountability, and trust in decision-making processes.

The evolution of Explainable AI (XAI) comes from the rising complexity of black-box AI models, which lack of transparency and interpretability in decision-making processes [47]. Early AI algorithms were more interpretable, but the shift to complex machine learning and deep learning increased the need for methods to explain outcomes [48]. XAI is crucial in domains where

understanding AI decisions is critical for accountability [49]. Moreover, it enhances user trust by providing insights into how AI systems reach specific conclusions [50].

However, applications of Explainable AI in manufacturing have been quite new and limited. The works by Thapaliya et. al. [51] presented a machine learning-based approach for predicting power consumption and processing time in CNC milling machines, using XAI techniques to explain key influencing factors for optimization however, its reliance on post-hoc explanations limits direct applicability in real-time quality control for cutting processes. Kumar et al. [52] proposed a human-guided approach using XAI combined with the EfficientNet-B0 model for accurately identifying tool wear states during the machining of IN718. While the method demonstrates scalability across varying cutting conditions, its practical applicability may be limited by the complexity of integration and the reliance on a labeled image dataset for diverse machining scenarios.

The research carried out by [53] reviewed several applications of XAI in manufacturing including explaining factory job classifications, and Shapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) based analysis for alloy composition effects. However, in spite of these works, the application of XAI directly to machining has been limited, except for a study by [54], which applies an interpretable AI approach for identifying the globally important time frequency bands in grinding. This opens up a gap in the scientific literature in application of XAI for part quality monitoring during machining.

Despite notable advancements in intelligent quality control for manufacturing, it is essential to explore the theoretical foundations that underpin these approaches mentioned in this work. The following section delves into the theoretical foundations of the article.

3. Theoretical background

Building upon the advancements discussed in the state-of-the-art, a deeper understanding of the theoretical principles is essential. This section delves into surface quality assessment, the machine learning models employed, and the role of Explainable AI in manufacturing.

3.1 Surface Quality assessment

Surface roughness is a key indicator of surface quality, with parameters such as Ra, Rz, Rsk, and Rku as defined in 21920 (ISO, 2021) are widely standardized and used in industry [55]. Ra, the arithmetic mean deviation, is the most common due to its simplicity, but additional descriptors are often required to capture different aspects of the surface. While these parameters remain essential, direct measurement during machining can be challenging. AI offers a practical solution by learning the nonlinear correlations between machining parameters, cutting signals, and these traditional surface roughness measures, enabling more efficient in-process assessment.

3.2 Machine Learning models

Machine learning models were chosen over advanced deep learning models for the AI modeling. Since support vector machines (SVM) and random forests (RF) require less data and computational resources than deep learning algorithms like convolutional neural networks (CNNs), they are preferred in situations where in-situ training is necessary and datasets are not very large. Moreover, tree-based models like RF are more interpretable in nature, providing insights into the relationships between input features and output predictions, which is crucial for understanding the underlying mechanisms of roughness detection.

Support Vector Machine

Cortes et al. [59] introduced support vector machines (SVMs) as a supervised learning technique initially developed for binary classification. The objective is to find the optimal hyperplane that separates or fits the data with the maximum margin while minimizing classification or regression errors. Given training examples (x_i, y_i) , the optimization problem is:

$$\min_{w,b} \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 + C \sum_{i=1}^n \xi_i \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

Where $\|w\|^2$ penalizes complex decision boundaries, C controls the trade-off between margin width and misclassification, and ξ_i are slack variables [60].

The decision function is expressed as:

$$f(x) = \text{sign}(\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i y_i K(x, x_i) + b) \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

where α_i are Lagrange multipliers, y_i the class labels, $K(x, x_i)$ the kernel function enabling nonlinear mapping, and the bias term b [61,62].

SVMs are effective in achieving high accuracy with limited data [63], but computational cost rises with large datasets and interpretability decreases in complex feature spaces. For machining applications, SVMs work well on structured process data (parameters, signals) but are less suited to highly unstructured or high-dimensional data, where training becomes resource-intensive and explanations less transparent.

Random Forest

The Random Forest (RF) algorithm, introduced by Breiman [64], is an ensemble method that aggregates the predictions of multiple decision trees trained on bootstrap samples. Each tree is

built using randomly selected subsets of predictors, which reduces correlation between trees and improves prediction accuracy [65]. The aggregated output of the forest is given by:

$$\hat{y} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N T_i(\mathbf{x}) \quad \text{Eq. (4)}$$

where N is the number of trees and $T_i(x)$ indicates the i^{th} decision tree's prediction for the input vector x

RFs also provide feature importance, which quantifies the contribution of each input to prediction performance. One formulation is:

$$I_j = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N \text{impurity}_t \cdot \text{split_count}_t}{\sum_{t=1}^N \text{split_count}_t} \quad \text{Eq. (5)}$$

where impurity reduction may be measured by Gini, entropy, or mean squared error depending on the task [66].

RFs are robust to noisy data, handle nonlinear relationships well, and offer interpretable feature importance. However, they can overfit with very deep trees and may struggle with highly unstructured data such as raw signals. In machining contexts, they are effective for structured process parameters and force, vibration signal features, but less suited to raw high-dimensional data without preprocessing.

Artificial Neural Networks

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) are computational models inspired by biological neural systems, consisting of interconnected neurons arranged in layers. Each neuron computes a weighted sum of its inputs plus a bias, passed through a nonlinear activation function such as sigmoid, tanh, or ReLU [67]. The basic formulation is:

$$a = f\left(\sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i + b\right) \quad \text{Eq. (6)}$$

where w_i are the connection weights, x_i the inputs, b the bias, and f the activation function.

By adjusting weights during training, ANNs can learn complex, nonlinear mappings between inputs and outputs, making them powerful for prediction tasks [67]. In manufacturing, they have been applied to forecast surface roughness by capturing hidden patterns across machining parameters and process signals [68].

ANNs offer strong predictive power and flexibility, especially with large datasets, but require significant data and tuning to avoid overfitting. For machining applications, they are well-suited when rich sensor data is available, but can be resource-intensive and less interpretable compared to simpler models.

The incorporation of Explainable AI (XAI) approaches is essential for building confidence and transparency in AI-driven surface quality evaluation. Before delving into the materials and methods used during the experimentation stage, the role of XAI in interpreting model predictions is first explored.

Explainable AI

Explainable AI (XAI) focuses on developing models whose decision-making processes are understandable, assuring transparency and interpretability [69]. Unlike typical AI models, which frequently serve as "black boxes," XAI demonstrates how inputs are turned into outputs, allowing users to comprehend, trust, and evaluate the findings while avoiding bias [70]. XAI's key properties are interpretability, transparency, and the ability to create human-readable explanations. Although the term is new, the topic of explainability has been there since the mid-1970s when researchers investigated explanations for expert systems [71]. XAI approaches can be broadly characterized as model-specific or model-agnostic. Model-specific approaches are developed for certain algorithms, such as decision trees, which are naturally interpretable. Two model-agnostic approaches, SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) and Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations (LIME), are used on models to provide post-hoc explanations by estimating model behavior or quantifying feature contributions [72].

Feature importance is a key concept that measures how much each input feature contributes to the model's predictions. One common approach is to permute the values of a feature and observe how much the model's prediction error changes [73]. If the error increases significantly, the feature is deemed important. If the model's performance remains the same, the feature is considered less relevant.

As for example, in the case of RF regression, the use the reduction in variance (or reduction in Mean Squared Error) to calculate feature importance. For each split in a decision tree, the change in MSE (variance reduction) is computed as :

$$\Delta MSE = MSE(t_{parent}) - \left(\frac{N_{left}}{N} MSE(t_{left}) + \frac{N_{right}}{N} \right) \quad \text{Eq. (7)}$$

where $MSE(t_{parent})$ is the Mean Squared Error at the parent node, $MSE(t_{left})$ and $MSE(t_{right})$ are the MSEs at the left and right child nodes, respectively, N_{left} and N_{right} are the number of samples in the left and right nodes and N is the total number of samples in the parent node.

The final importance of a feature is calculated as the normalized sum of its contributions across the entire forest given by:

$$Feature\ Importance = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{s=1}^S \Delta MSE_{s,t} \quad Eq. (8)$$

where T is given as the total number of trees in the forests and S as the number of splits involving the particular feature [40].

The theoretical background establishes the foundation for understanding surface quality assessment, the machine learning models employed, and the importance of Explainable AI in interpreting results. An AI-aided approach is favorable as it can effectively assess intricate, nonlinear correlations among surface roughness, machining parameters, and cutting signals, yielding more precise and predictive insights. Building on this framework, the following section will detail the experimental setup for the manufacturing process and data collection used in this study.

4. Materials and Experimental Design

In this study, the workpiece material selected was Aluminum alloy 2017A, known for its high strength and suitability many industrial and military applications. A series of surface milling cuts were performed on a 5-Axis Mill-Turn Machine using a 20 mm diameter milling cutter R217.69-1020.RE-12-2AN with two carbide inserts XOEX120408FR-E06 H15 from SECO, and a synthetic emulsion of water and Ecocool CS+ (~5%) as cutting fluid. In Figure 1, it is schematically presented a summary of the whole experimental setup for the data generation. Starting from a), the experimental setup features a STIL-Marposs chromatic confocal sensor CL1-MG210 for measuring surface roughness, and a piezoelectric Kistler dynamometer Model 9257B for force measurement at 10 kHz of acquisition rate. In b) is presented the surface milling cutting strategy, where each radial pass of the tool (cuts #1, #2, ..., n) corresponds to a unique combination of cutting parameters (see Table 1). Additionally, for each cut, six surface linear profiles with a length of $\Delta L_{measurement}$ are measured. In c) is shown how the 3-axes force signals are transformed into active force F_a and normal force F_z and then trimmed per cut using a window length of $\Delta t_{measurement}$ so that the force signal to be analyzed corresponds exactly to the 15 mm ($\Delta L_{measurement}$) of surface roughness profiles that were measured. The post-processing of the six surface roughness profiles per cut is done using MountainsMap® which outputs the roughness parameters shown in d).

Figure 1 – a) Experimental Setup for the cutting experiments. b) Surface milling strategy. c) Force acquisition and post-processing. d) On-machine surface roughness measurement and post-processing.

Based on the literature on milling, it is well-established that the key process variables influencing surface roughness are depth of cut, cutting speed, and feed rate [74]. Therefore, a full factorial design was employed in this study, considering three factors—cutting speed, depth of cut, and feed rate : each with five levels. The experiments were designed with arbitrary machining parameters to get an approximately equal number of surface roughness classes. Table 1 outlines the cutting parameters utilized in the study. In total, 125 cutting conditions per cutting mode were tested, totalizing 250 different surfaces, 500 force signals (Fa and Fz), and 1500 roughness profiles.

Machining Parameter	Values
Feed Rate	0.15, 0.25, 0.45, 0.65, 0.85 [mm/rot]
Depth of Cut	0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5 [mm]
Cutting Speed	250, 350, 400, 600, 800 [m/min]

Table 1 - Machining parameters used for the up and down milling experiments.

Moreover, two types of cutting modes were used in this work: **up** and **down** milling. Figure 2 schematically shows the cutting strategy on the workpiece surfaces, with color coding for chip formation in each mode and a breakdown into three phases: initial contact (1), transition (2), and final phase (3). In up milling (shown in blue layout), the physical process of chip formation follows a thin-to-thick pattern. Phase 1 begins with initial contact and friction, as the cutter lightly engages the material with a thin chip entry, resulting in high friction and heat due to limited material displacement. In phase 2, the elastic to plastic transition occurs as the chip thickens, with the material reaching its yield point and transitioning into plastic deformation, allowing more effective material removal. Finally, in phase 3, full plastic deformation and shearing take place, where the chip reaches its maximum thickness, dominated by plastic deformation and high shear stress near the cutting edge. This thickened final phase requires greater forces for chip removal, in contrast to the smoother, controlled surface finish achieved in down milling [75]. Conversely, in down milling, shown in red, chip formation follows a thick-to-thin pattern. In phase 1, the initial contact and full plastic deformation occur, where the cutter engages the material with maximum chip thickness, enabling immediate plastic deformation and efficient shearing with reduced initial friction. In phase 2, progressive shearing and chip thinning follow as the tool continues its rotation, with decreasing chip thickness and smoother material flow along the shear plane, further minimizing friction. By phase 3, the final phase of minimal friction is reached, with the chip thinned to its minimum, usually reducing heat generation [76]. Thus, we can conclude that the physics governing up-milling and down-milling processes are quite the opposite in nature. Kaltenbrunner et al. [77] concisely summarized these phenomena through experimentation, highlighting how the differences in thermomechanical loading and tool wear between up-milling and down-milling

processes, specifically in machining titanium alloy Ti-6Al-4V, result in accelerated tool wear in up-milling due to the combined effects of thermal and mechanical loading.

Figure 2 – Schematic representation of up (top) and down (bottom) milling modes for the surface milling experiments based on the classical works of [75][76][78].

Continuing with Figure 2, as the tool progresses toward the center of the workpiece, the radial engagement of the tool diminishes. This variation introduces complexity to the database

concerning cutting forces, as each pass of an insert involves a distinct duration of engagement in the cutting process. This is also illustrated in Figure 2 by the difference of radial engagement $a_{e,i}$ and $a_{e,v}$, which represent the first passage (i), and the fifth passage (v) of an insert respectively. A preliminary cut with full radial engagement (Precut), shown in Figure 2, is performed but excluded from the dataset as it does not correspond to either up or down milling.

An additional factor influencing the experimental database was the wiper feature of the inserts. Figure 3 illustrates a face mill cutter performing a surfacing operation (in a), with a zoomed-in detail on the tool tip, demonstrating how the chip forms during the cutting process. The roughness profile of the milled surface at the center of the tool path (in b) allows for an estimation of the kinematic roughness R_t based on the tool nose radius R_ϵ and the feed rate per rotation per tooth f_z . For a tool without a wiper feature, the kinematic roughness R_t can be estimated as shown (in c). However, when a wiper feature is present, the kinetic roughness decreases significantly, theoretically approaching zero (in d). The entire experimental database used in this work was generated with milling inserts featuring a wiper geometry.

Figure 3 – Depiction of chip formation and effect of wiper feature on surface roughness in face milling based on [78] [X].

The collected data from the experimental setup is subsequently processed and analyzed to extract meaningful insights, which are discussed in the following section

5. Methodology: Data Processing and Modelling

5.1 Pre-processing of force data

Following the completion of the cutting experiments, the data was processed for AI-aided downstream analysis. Initially, both spatial (as seen in Figure 4) and temporal (as seen in Figure 5) features were evaluated. However, the final analysis concentrated on time-domain properties since they were more directly connected to the cutting forces, which were the study's major emphasis.

Force signals in milling processes exhibit distinct characteristics depending on whether the operation is up milling or down milling. Although the first downstream analysis was first conducted in the frequency domain using the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT), there were no visible variations in spectrograms between up and down milling under identical cutting settings. A complementary Power Spectral Density (PSD) analysis was conducted, Figure 4, for F_a with $v_c = 600\text{m/min}$, $a_p = 0.3\text{ mm}$ and $f = 0.25\text{ mm/rotation}$, to investigate the signal characteristics in frequency domain. Except for down milling exhibiting higher amplitude in higher frequencies (above $\sim 4000\text{ Hz}$), the PSD results showed that the force signals lacked distinct frequency-domain features that could effectively differentiate the two milling processes.

Figure 4 – The Power Spectral Density of the active force component (F_a) with spindle speed 600m/min, depth of cut 0.3 mm and feed rate 0.25 mm/rotation.

In contrast, time-domain analysis, Figure 5, captured significant variations in force magnitude and pattern over time, directly reflecting the intermittent nature of chip formation in up and down-milling. Since cutting forces are inherently influenced by tool engagement, material removal, and cutting edge interactions, the time-domain features proved to be more sensitive and effective in distinguishing between the two processes. It is particularly valuable in this context, as it captures the dynamic changes in force and the transient behaviors specific to each milling mode. Time

domain analysis accurately captures these temporal force fluctuations, allowing for a thorough study of the milling process's stability and efficiency as seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Fa component (active) of cutting force observed during 1 cutting process along with its lobe-wise comparison of the forces in up and down milling with spindle speed 600m/min, depth of cut 0.3 mm and feed rate 0.25 mm/rotation.

Following the preprocessing of the force signals, the subsequent step involves feature extraction, which is essential for converting the processed data into meaningful and concise representations. The following section lays the foundation for systematic analysis by capturing essential characteristics from the signals to enable further pattern identification and interpretation.

5.2 Feature extraction :

Once the signals have been processed, it was ready for the next downstream analysis. Signal feature extraction is critical in transforming raw signal data into a concise and useful representation, collecting crucial properties required for analysis, pattern identification,

interpretation, and storage. This approach enables the effective use of signals in a wide range of applications.

The initial consideration of the feature extraction step was to figure out the domain for the downstream analysis of the signals. A Python script was used to create a CSV file for systematic downstream analysis. This file contained the features extracted from the signals for both up and down milling alongside the machining parameters for each of the milling processes. From the signals, a number of temporal features were retrieved. Table 2 presents the set of statistical features (mean, RMS, variance, standard deviation, etc.) extracted from the cutting force signals. These descriptors are standard time-domain features, consistently applied in machining signal analysis and tool condition monitoring to characterize process dynamics, with their use well established in the scientific literature for over a decade.[XX, XXX, XXXX, XXXXX]

Table 2 - List of statistical features extracted from the cutting force signals.

Feature extracted	Formula	Definition
Mean	$\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right)$	The average value of the signal.
RMS	$x_{RMS} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} (x_1^2 + x_2^2 + \dots + x_n^2)}$	The square root of the mean square, the average of squared values within a set or group.
Variance	$Var(x) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2$	The expected value of the squared deviation from the mean.
Std. Dev	$s = \sqrt{\frac{1}{(n-1)} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}$	The statistical metric that indicates the degree of variability from the mean.
Peak	$x_{peak} = \max(f(x)) = f(x^*) \text{ if } f(x^*) \geq f(x) \text{ for all } x \text{ in } X$	The maximum peak value.
Peak to peak values	$A_{pp} = \max(f(x)) - \min(f(x))$	The value range (maximum - minimum) of amplitude.
Crest Factor	$CF = \frac{x_{peak}}{x_{RMS}}$	The feature to indicate how extreme the peaks are in a waveform.

Skewness

$$\gamma = \frac{n}{(n-1)(n-2)} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{x_i - \bar{x}}{s} \right)^3$$

The measure of the asymmetry of the probability distribution of a real-valued random variable about its mean.

Kurtosis

$$\kappa = \frac{n(n+1)}{(n-1)(n-2)(n-3)} \cdot \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i - \bar{x}}{s} \right)^4 - \frac{3(n-1)^2}{(n-2)(n-3)}$$

The statistical measure of the degree of peakedness in a data distribution

Apart from these features, the response of each force lobe to the cutting processes was also examined. When the milling cutter completes one rotation, the number of force peaks should be proportional to the number of teeth on the cutter, maintaining consistency. However, variances on peak shape may arise owing to machining complexity or minor height difference between teeth. These discrepancies, as indicated in Figure 6 are regarded as elements influencing the workpiece's final surface roughness. As a result, in addition to examining the overall signal properties, the information from each lobe must be considered independently and thus the idea of feature extraction of every single lobe of both Fa and Fz signals.

5.3 Feature processing

Apart from these features, the response of each force lobe to the cutting processes was also examined. For each full rotation of the milling cutter, the number of force peaks should be proportional to the number of teeth on the cutter, maintaining consistency. In Figure 6, a milling cutter with two teeth performing a surface milling process is shown. As the tool advances with a feed rate per tooth of fz, the undeformed chip thickness is depicted in (a). In (b), the theoretical resulting force, which could be either Fa or Fz for this study, is illustrated. The passage of each insert generates one lobe, and variances in peak shape may arise due to machining complexity or minor height differences between teeth, represented as Δh in (c). These discrepancies lead to a change in force, denoted as ΔF, as shown in (b), and are regarded as factors influencing the workpiece's final surface roughness. As a result, in addition to examining the overall signal properties, the information from each lobe must be considered independently, thus introducing the idea of feature extraction for every single lobe of both Fa and Fz signals.

Figure 6 - Absolute differences in force peaks.

Each measured F_a and F_z signals in time domain were trimmed at both the beginning and the end during pre-processing, resulting in a signal window of duration $\Delta t_{measurement}$. To locate peaks, the first derivative approach is utilized, which involves computing the rate of change of the signal at each point and locating zero crossings where the slope changes sign, as well as evaluating the behavior of the first derivative. The amplitude of each data point is then compared to that of its neighbors. To improve this detection, additional horizontal and vertical thresholds are specified. This amplitude threshold is defined by the signal's properties as well as the required peak detection sensitivity. Apart from this, to avoid spurious small peaks, a threshold was set based on the distance between two peaks which is inversely proportional to the cutting speed of the tool. To get this distance, the following Eq (9) was used:

$$T = \frac{60 \cdot \pi \cdot D}{1000 \cdot V_c \cdot Z} \quad \text{Eq. (9)}$$

where Z is the number of teeth on the milling cutter, V_c is the cutting speed (m/min), D is the cutting tool's diameter (mm), and T is the time it takes for one tooth to pass (in seconds). This along with the acquisition rate, gave us the minimum distance between the peaks of the signal.

Once the peaks are detected, localizing them within a window involves determining the width of each peak denoted by d in Figure 7. This was achieved by finding the minima points on either side of the peaks where the signal drops below a certain relative amplitude threshold.

Figure 7 describes the process of localizing detected peaks within a specified window by determining the width of each peak, denoted as d . This is accomplished by identifying the minima on either side of the peaks where the signal amplitude falls below a defined relative threshold.

A relative amplitude threshold, denoted by h was set as a fraction of the peak value and was determined to measure the peak width. This threshold was employed to mark the level at which the peak width is assessed. This was kept at 97% of the starting from the peak index, the signal was traversed left and right until the signal values dropped below the relative height threshold. These points were then identified as the boundaries of the peak width. The width of each peak

was subsequently calculated by subtracting the indices of the left boundary from the right boundary. Thus, by localizing these lobes, statistical features were extracted from the lobes.

The described process was automated using a Python script, which generated a structured dataset containing the extracted features along with machining parameters, including whether the data originated from up or down milling. These features provide critical insights into the characteristics of cutting force signals, particularly the lobes, facilitating downstream analysis in applications such as condition monitoring, tool wear assessment etc.

The extracted features were subsequently employed to train the machine learning models to identify patterns and relationships within the data. The following section details the model training process, including, hyperparameter selection.

Figure 7 - Localization of the lobes of the cutting force which were used for feature extraction.

5.4 Model Training

Following the preparation of the dataset with the extracted features, the next step involved training the models for surface roughness prediction. For this, three different machine learning models were used: Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Random Forests (RF), and Support Vector Machines (SVM). These models were selected based on their ability to capture complex patterns within the data, as well as their relevance to the study objectives. However, since we had a vast dataset with varied extracted features, it was essential to tune the hyperparameters of the model to achieve the best results. A two-step approach was employed to select the hyperparameters: an initial random search followed by fine-tuning with grid search. Both of them were performed with 10-fold cross-validation to ensure robustness and generalizability of the trained model.

First, the models were trained with a random search to find the approximate search space. Random search is a powerful hyperparameter optimization strategy that randomly selects a set number of hyperparameter combinations. The phases consist of establishing the model and

hyperparameters, determining their value ranges, and randomly choosing a set number of possibilities from the grid for assessment. Once the grid values were roughly estimated, grid search was used to finetune the best-case parameter search.

The Random Forest (RF) model's key hyperparameters were the number of trees in the forest, the maximum depth of each tree, the minimum number of samples required to split an internal node, and the minimum number of samples per leaf. For the Support Vector Machine (SVM), the regularization parameter, kernel type, and kernel-specific parameters such as gamma were tuned. The number of hidden layers, the number of neurons per layer, and the learning rate were the main optimization criteria for artificial neural networks (ANNs).

At this stage, an essential criterion to examine is the bias-variance tradeoff. It is a key concept in predictive modelling that considers the relationship between a model's accuracy on training data (low bias) and its ability to generalize to new data (low variance). High bias can result in underfitting, where the model is too simple to identify the underlying patterns, whereas high variance can result in overfitting, where the model is too complex and captures noise from the training data. K-fold cross-validation was utilized to avoid these biases which is a technique for evaluating the performance of a model by dividing the data into multiple equal-sized folds and training it k times using a bootstrapped dataset.

$$Loss = Loss_{original} + \lambda \sum_{i=1}^n w_i^2 \quad \text{Eq. (10)}$$

For further regularization, L2-regularization was used by adding a penalty term to the loss as seen in Eq. (10). In the next section, we discuss the evaluation metrics used to evaluate the model.

5.5 Evaluation Metrics

Evaluating the prediction models involves assessing how well the model predicts continuous outcomes. Common evaluation metrics include Mean Absolute Error (MAE), which quantifies the average magnitude of prediction errors regardless of direction, and Mean Squared Error (MSE), which calculates the average squared difference between actual and predicted values, giving greater weight to larger errors. MAE provides a direct average error, making it more interpretable, while MSE penalizes outliers more heavily. In regression tasks, MAE ensures robust performance across varied errors, whereas MSE prioritizes minimizing large deviations, potentially reducing generalization in certain cases. Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) is derived from MSE and expresses the error in the same units as the target variable, making it suitable for model comparison. The evaluation metrics' formulas are given by:

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad \text{Eq. (21)}$$

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad \text{Eq. (32)}$$

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad \text{Eq. (43)}$$

For the auxiliary classification model, confusion matrices are used however to evaluate the efficacy of different categorizations between the milling types. Predicted numbers from all approaches are listed as entries in the uncertainty matrix. The data numbers are shown in each area. The matrix's axis reflects properly classified data, such as true positives and true negatives. It is a table that summarizes a classifier's predictions by comparing the predicted and actual classes. The matrix is made up of four main components: True Positives (TP), True Negatives (TN), False Positives (FP), and False Negatives (FN). These components aid in the calculation of performance measures such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{True Positive (TP)}}{\text{True Positive (TP)} + \text{False Positive (FP)}} \quad \text{Eq. (54)}$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{True Positive (TP)}}{\text{True Positive (TP)} + \text{False Negative (FN)}} \quad \text{Eq. (65)}$$

6. Results and Discussion

The cutting forces resulting from the chip removal process are directly proportional to the depth of cut (a_p) and feed rate (f). As illustrated in Figure 2, chip formation varies significantly between up and down milling. In up milling, where the cut begins predominantly with friction, higher energy consumption and greater forces are expected compared to down milling under the same cutting conditions, based on fundamental chip formation principles. This general behavior is also reported in the literature [78]. Our experimental results conform to this predicted behavior. Figure 8 and Figure 9 show that the average active force (F_a) increases with depth of cut due to the larger uncut chip cross-section, while the normal force (F_z) initially increases but decreases at higher depths of cut due to the influence of the positive rake face pulling the tool axially toward the workpiece.

Figure 8 – Active force F_a vs depth of cut a_p for different feed rates and cutting modes.

Figure 9 – Normal force F_z vs depth of cut a_p for different feed rates and cutting modes.

To begin, the proposed lobe-based features produced very positive outcomes in the auxiliary classification model targeted at discriminating between up milling and down milling utilizing features extracted from cutting force signals in the time domain and process parameters. These lobe-based characteristics, which capture periodic and harmonic aspects of the cutting force signals, provide light on the unique dynamic behaviors of up and down milling processes. The RF model, known for its capacity to handle complicated feature interactions and non-linear

correlations, beat other models on the test dataset. Furthermore, its integrated feature importance evaluation process guarantees that the most relevant elements of lobe-based features are used effectively, resulting in improved classification accuracy. Figure 10 shows the classification results with the help of a confusion matrix for the RF model on a test set. It indicates that the classification model using the lobe-based approach correctly identified 21 instances of up/down milling (True Negatives) and 11 instances (True Positives) while 3 cases were misclassified as the opposite class in both False Positive and False Negative categories with 0 representing the down milling and 1 representing the up milling.

Figure 10- A confusion matrix of the classification model using the lobe-based approach.

The first regression model was trained on the entire set of the features extracted. This step was carried out without any specific feature selection step with an 80-20 train-test ratio. Following hyperparameter tuning, the optimal values for each model were identified based on cross-validation performance. For the RF model, the optimal number of trees was set to 24, with a maximum depth of 85 and a minimum sample split of 2. The best SVM configuration included a Radial Basis Function kernel (RBF) with a regularization parameter of 3. In the ANN model, the final architecture consisted of 3 hidden layers, utilizing "relu" as the activation function, a learning rate of 0.001, and a batch size of 32. These selections resulted in improved predictive accuracy while maintaining a balance between model complexity and generalization. Once the model was trained, its important features were identified using feature importance graphs. For the RF model, it has its implicit feature importance attribute which was further used for feature selection. As for the SVM model, Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) was used. It is a feature selection strategy that iteratively eliminates the least important elements from a model to reveal the most relevant ones. It iteratively trains the model, ranking features in order of relevance, and removing the least important until the target number of features is obtained.

Figure 11- Feature Importance graph from the RF model showing high importance of the lobe-based features extracted

The feature importance graph in Figure 11, after the first round of training, indicates that characteristics derived from cutting force signals are prioritized over machining parameters, with a strong focus on signal form and distribution. This prioritization stems from the direct interaction between cutting forces and the milling process dynamics, including up and down milling. Features such as peak values, skewness, and kurtosis effectively capture the material removal process and tool interactions, making them crucial for surface roughness prediction. These properties provide insights for cutting efficiency and surface finish quality, both essential in milling. Even though cutting speed, feed rate, and depth of cut are important machining parameters, they do not fully capture the complex physical phenomenon of chip formation. Thus, the ML model prioritizes the features extracted from the force signal, offering a more detailed and dynamic representation of cutting. This leads to more accurate and reliable surface roughness estimations.

Model	MSE		MAE		Accuracy	
	A	B	A	B	A	B
RF regression	0.024	0.015	0.14	0.11	-	
SVM regression	0.022	0.018	0.28	0.16	-	
ANN regression	0.026	0.020	0.15	0.13	-	
RF classification	-	-	-	-	77.4%	85.2%
SVM classification	-	-	-	-	73.9%	82.6%

Table 3 - Results of different cases both the regression and the classification model and its general improvement with the lobe-based approach. The column A denotes the results of the model where features were extracted from the entire signal and B where features were extracted from the lobe-based approach.

When the model was trained using lobe-based features extracted from cutting force signals, these features proved to be the most crucial for surface roughness prediction, as shown in Figure 11. Their importance lies in capturing periodic variations in the cutting force, which reflect the milling process's stability and dynamics, directly influencing surface quality. The incorporation of lobe-based features into the model resulted in a considerable reduction in prediction loss, demonstrating its efficiency in enhancing accuracy and robustness. Following the identification of the top six important features from the feature importance plot having almost 70% of the explainable variance, the model was retrained using only these features, resulting in a streamlined model with a shorter training time. In this simplified plan of action, the RF model outperformed the SVM model. This performance discrepancy is due to RF's intrinsic capabilities in handling high-dimensional data and capturing complicated relationships between features. RFs, as an ensemble learning approach, use the combined power of several decision trees to increase accuracy and robustness while successfully minimizing variance and avoiding overfitting. They also naturally manage feature importance, giving a solid foundation for using the most predictive characteristics. SVMs, on the other hand, while effective for classification tasks, struggle with the complexity and non-linearity of the feature set, particularly when the connections between features are complicated. As a result of its capacity to better capture and generalize these associations, the RF model outperformed giving it a better choice for predicting surface roughness. The results of the respective models are reported in Table 3. It shows that the MSE is slightly higher than the MAE, suggesting that the model's prediction mistakes are modest and consistent. MSE's sensitivity to greater mistakes, as demonstrated by discrepancy squaring, reveals a few relatively significant errors but no severe outliers. This balance shows that the model performs well, successfully controlling usual predicted deviations while minimizing outlier effects. To further validate the feature importance ranking, a permutation residual analysis was conducted by training two models: one with the top six ranked features and another with the bottom six. The model with top-ranked features showed lower residuals, while the bottom-ranked feature model exhibited significantly higher residuals as can be seen in Figure 12. This validates the feature importance ranking, confirming that the highest-ranked features contribute more to predictive accuracy and reinforcing the reliability of our initial analysis.

Figure 12 – Visualization of the residuals comparing models trained on top- and bottom-ranked features based on the feature importance plot. Each test Point on the x-axis corresponds to an unseen machining trial in the held-out test set. The y-axis shows the measured and predicted Ra values (μm), with the dotted lines indicating the residuals between them.

In the final set of experiments, other roughness parameters alongside as Ra (average roughness) such as Rsk (skewness), Rku (kurtosis), and Rz (average maximum height of the profile), served as ground truth for surface roughness estimate using cutting force signals and process parameters one at a time. The results showed that, aside from Ra, the Rsk parameter performed exceptionally well. This may be explained by the nature of the Rsk parameter, which assesses the asymmetry of the surface profile distribution. Unlike Ra, which calculates a fundamental aggregate of surface deviations, Rsk collects more specific information about the profile's shape, showing whether the profile has more peaks or valleys. This makes Rsk extremely sensitive to chip formation, as

represented in the cutting force signals. Although Ra is a sought-after roughness parameter because of its simplicity and ease of interpretation, it is insensitive to surface topographical differences, as different surfaces can have the same Ra while having diverse functional features. The model predicts Ra better than Rsk, given that Ra is easier to predict as it is an average, providing a stable global measure of roughness. In contrast, Rsk is more functional and is more sensitive to capturing the asymmetry and the peaks, making it more challenging for the model to learn. Nevertheless, Rsk is a more functionally significant attribute since it describes the asymmetry of height distribution, which influences functionalities like lubricant retention, wear resistance, and load-bearing capacity. This makes Rsk especially important in applications like tribology, sealing interfaces, and biomedical implants, where surface functionality is key [79].

Thus, lobe-based features from these signals, when combined with process parameters, can better predict surface properties obtained by Rsk. This increased sensitivity to profile asymmetry most likely adds to Rsk's efficacy in estimating surface roughness, making it a useful measure alongside Ra for assessing overall surface quality. A comparative analysis of these results can be found in Figure 13.

Figure 13 - Comparison of the results with different roughness parameters studied using RF.

7. Conclusionss

In this work, an experimental database was developed by milling aluminum on a CNC mill-turn center, focusing on surface roughness measured on-machine using a chromatic confocal

profilometer and cutting force recorded with a dynamometer. A physics-based approach was proposed, considering chip formation mechanics in up milling, where friction leads to elastic-to-plastic deformation and shearing, and down milling, where plastic deformation precedes progressive shearing with minimal friction. Feature extraction was applied to force lobes in the time domain, with lobe-based time series analysis providing insights into surface quality, validated by feature importance plots. The approach remained robust despite challenges like varying tool radial engagement and wiper inserts enhancing surface finish, which complicate direct correlations between cutting parameters and surface quality.

Lobe-based features were also explored for auxiliary classification models distinguishing up and down milling, with RF models excelling due to their interpretability and ability to manage complex interactions. SVM and RF were preferred over deep learning models to balance predictive accuracy with computational efficiency, essential for real-time manufacturing applications. Feature selection, using RF's implicit importance and SVM's Recursive Feature Elimination, further optimized performance.

The study demonstrated the importance of lobe-based features in predicting surface roughness and confirmed Rsk's role in assessing profile asymmetry, which complements Ra in a comprehensive evaluation. Ultimately, AI-driven on-machine quality control can reduce part scrapping by accurately predicting surface roughness based on machining parameters and cutting forces. This work contributes by going beyond black-box AI and providing interpretable insights into machining mechanics. Nevertheless, future works will depend on addressing current limitations, particularly the restricted roughness range of the database. Expanding the database and incorporating additional sensing modalities such as vibration, temperature, and humidity will be essential to further strengthen the robustness and industrial applicability of the proposed approach.

8. Future Research

In this study, force signals were utilized to predict and correlate surface roughness. Lobe-based feature extraction proved to be a reliable indicator for varying radial tool engagements with a wiper feature under different cutting strategies (up and down milling). Using an AI model, we successfully distinguished the effects of cutting physics between up and down milling through force signals. However, the current model has limitations in generalization due to a restricted roughness range in the database. Expanding the database to encompass a broader spectrum of roughness levels would enhance robustness. Future research aims to integrate additional sensors, such as vibration, temperature, and humidity sensors, to provide a more comprehensive view of physics of the machining process.

Furthermore, this study utilized unworn tools, and incorporating tool wear in future research would help capture changes in wear signatures over time. The use of a 3-axis dynamometer, though effective, poses challenges in industrial settings due to cost, setup complexity, and structural stiffness variations. To address this, the lobe-based prediction models developed here could be adapted for setups using force-measuring pins instead. These sensors can be easily installed in the machine tool structure with minimal interference while effectively capturing mechanical stresses.

The ultimate goal is to establish a Proactive Quality Control (PQC) model integrating predictive capabilities and feedback control to dynamically monitor and adjust machining processes using AI agents, as illustrated in Figure 14. By aligning predictions with a correction model, we aim to ensure accuracy, enabling real-time adaptations and achieving consistent, high-quality manufacturing outcomes.

Figure 14 – A blueprint for an AI agent-driven Proactive Quality Control (PQC) framework in machining operation.

However, several key challenges remain open for exploration:

- Now with multiple additional sensory signals—such as spindles' rotation and torque, 3-axis vibration, position and speed of machine axes, power consumption, and other sensor outputs—are available, which of these parameters truly contribute to improving the PQC model with higher importance?
- How should the effectiveness of the PQC system be assessed? Should the primary evaluation metric be surface roughness, dimensional accuracy, or tool wear, or should it involve a multi-criteria decision framework that balances all these factors?

These open questions pave the way for future research, guiding the next steps toward a fully adaptive and intelligent machining process. Addressing them will be crucial in realizing a framework that predicts and adaptively learns deviations in a continual learning setup, ensuring optimal manufacturing outcomes.

9. Declarations

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The authors declare that they have no competing financial or non-financial interests.

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